

1 **Facial blushing and feather fluffing are indicators of emotions in domestic fowl (*Gallus***
2 ***gallus domesticus*)**

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18 **Abstract**

19 The study of facial expressions in mammals provided great advances in the identification of
20 their emotions and then in the comprehension of their sentience. So far, this area of research
21 has excluded birds. With a naturalist approach, we analysed facial blushing and feather displays
22 in domestic hens. Hens were filmed in situations contrasting in emotional valence and arousal
23 level: situations known to indicate calm states (positive valence / low arousal), have rewarding
24 effects (positive valence / high arousal) or induce fear-related behaviour (negative valence /
25 high arousal). Head feather position as well as skin redness of comb, wattles, ear lobes and
26 cheeks varied across these situations. Skin of all four areas was less red in situations with low
27 arousal compared to situations with higher arousal. Furthermore, skin redness of the cheeks and
28 ear lobes also varied depending on the valence of the situation: redness was higher in situations
29 with negative valence compared to situations with positive valence. We conclude that hens have
30 facial displays that reveal their emotions and that blushing is not exclusive to humans. This
31 opens a promising way to explore the emotional lives of birds, which is a critical step when
32 trying to improve poultry welfare.

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35 **Introduction**

36 Faces generate visual information that can be interpreted by conspecifics. This rich source of
37 information has arguably led to the development of face-specialized neural cortical areas in
38 several animal species including humans [1]. Facial expressions defined as movements of the
39 face [2] have been widely studied in human and non-human mammals. They play a key role
40 particularly in intra-specific communication. According to de Waal [3] “facial displays likely

41 evolved in tandem with the ability to decode them so as to infer the emotional state of others”.

42 Facial expressions provide information both on the internal state of the sender (expression of

43 the emotional experience) and its intent to engage in a particular behaviour [3-6]. As a

44 consequence, emotional expressions have adaptive functions since they participate to the

45 regulation of the interactions between conspecifics.

46

47 Studies of facial expressions have led to substantial advances in our understanding of the

48 emotional experiences of nonhuman mammals and how these expressions are involved in

49 communication between conspecifics [7]. Facial expressions have been described and studied

50 in numerous species: primates but also more recently domestic mammals such as dogs, cats,

51 horses [8], pigs [6] and mice [9]. However, facial expressions as a means to indicate emotional

52 experiences may not be a mammal specificity. Despite the reservation of some scientist due to

53 the lack of studies (e.g. [7]), birds could be concerned as well. As mentioned by Emery and

54 Clayton [10] birds have the means to produce facial expressions using head crest or facial

55 feathers. However, the movement of facial feathers has rarely been studied except in a few bird

56 species such as the red-vented bulbul [11]. Yet, identifying bird facial expression would provide

57 a useful tool for exploring and better understanding how they perceive and react to their social

58 and physical environment. This would increase the knowledge acquired on the adaptive value

59 that facial displays have for the social species. In addition, accessing the meaning of their facial

60 displays would be of great interest to promote appropriate interactions (positive ones) between

61 birds and humans. This is an ethical question, particularly in case of domestic species.

62

63 In addition to muscle movements of the face, face colour contributes to emotion expression in

64 humans. Blushing of specific facial areas varies with emotions and this information helps to

65 more readily decode emotions of the sender [12], particularly in the case of confusing muscular

66 expressions [13]. Avian species have high spectral sensitivity, elaborate cones and a rich set of
67 pigment [14-15]. Many birds are very colourful and feather colours are used as signals by
68 conspecifics in a lot of contexts: reproduction, mate selection, parental care and agonistic
69 situations. The colour of pigmented bare parts of the body such as legs, bills, appendices (e.g.
70 caruncles in red-legged partridge) or eye-rings can change depending on environmental
71 conditions (e.g. feeding conditions [16]). The colour of some of these bare parts reflects
72 individual health status, and therefore might affect mate choice by signalling the quality of the
73 sexual partner [17]. Transient changes of skin colour have also been reported, during intra-
74 specific social interaction or during human interaction [18-20], but have never been studied in
75 depth in relation to emotions. The domestic fowl provides an ideal model to study the capacity
76 to express transient skin colour variations of the face (from pale to red) in relation with
77 emotions. This species possesses exposed bare skin areas on their face. In addition, their face
78 is known to play a key role in communication. Head and neck are of greater importance than
79 the rest of the body in individual recognition [21] and appendices of the face, such as the comb,
80 seem to be an indicator of the ability of an individual to dominate a conspecific during dyadic
81 encounters (e.g. [22]). Furthermore, the emotional behaviour of this farmed species is well
82 documented (e.g. [23-25]).

83

84 Our objective was to explore the ability of hens to express facial expressions. The evidence of
85 such a capacity would be a big step to go further into the comprehension of their emotional
86 capacities. This would help to assess their sentience. Furthermore, knowing their emotional
87 experience is a critical step when trying to improve their welfare. To do so, we used a
88 naturalistic approach in two groups of rustic hens. Indeed, we are convinced like Bekoff [26]
89 that “field research on behaviour is of paramount importance for learning more about animal
90 emotions, because emotions have evolved in specific contexts”. We observed feather position

91 and skin colour of the face while hens expressed their daily routine behaviours (resting, feeding,
92 preening, dustbathing, and alert in response to a frightening stimulus) and during two test
93 situations (rewarding and capture test). These seven contexts were contrasted in both emotional
94 valence (positive/pleasant or negative/unpleasant emotions) and arousal level (high or low
95 intensity), two dimensions that constitute a functional framework widely used to study human
96 and non-human animal emotions [27]. Our hypothesis was that hens express facial expression
97 using the feather position and the colour of their face. We expected that head feather position
98 and the colour of their face varied depending on their current situation, i.e. their current
99 emotional experience. We also wanted to determine if similarities in feather position, or in the
100 colour of their face, would exist in the situations of similar emotional valence and arousal level.

101

102

103 **Material and methods**

104

105 **Ethics**

106 Behavioural observations are not considered as experimentations and are beyond the scope for
107 ethical consideration regarding French and European animal experimentation regulations.
108 Therefore, the Ethics Committee for Animal Experimentation of Val de Loire (CEEA Vdl,
109 CEEA - 019), considered that ethical approval was not required for this study (Protocol number:
110 CE19 – 2022-1310 – 1).

111 Animals investigated were commercial domestic hens reared in free range condition. Farmers
112 provided free access to their farm to perform our observations. After the experiment, all hens
113 were sold or given to an association.

114

115 **Animals and sites**

116 We investigated two groups of domestic hens (*Gallus gallus domesticus*): ten Pekin bantam
117 reared in a commercial farm (Le Haut Montmartre élevage, 37340 Cléré-les-pins, France) and
118 eight Meusienne, a local French strain, reared by a private breeder (M. Audureau) involved in
119 the conservation of local breeds (Chanteraine, 37800 Sainte Maure de Touraine, France). Pekin
120 (P-hens) and Meusienne (M-hens) are two strains known for their calmness and closeness with
121 humans. Furthermore, these strains are more appropriate to study skin colour variations of the
122 face than strains highly selected on production criteria. Indeed, some breeders selected these
123 later based on the comb shape and colour. Hens were studied in their rearing environment and
124 care was provided by their owner: M. Leduc for P-hens and M. Audureau for M-hens. They
125 were 2 to 3 months-old when filmed for this study. They lived in wooded areas covered with
126 grass (P-hens: 13.3 m x 16 m; M-hens: 25 m x 14.5 m) and had permanent access to a henhouse
127 containing perches and wood-shavings. Food (mixture of seeds and minerals) and water were
128 provided *ad libitum*. The experiments were performed in summer (late June to august 2020) in
129 sunny weather conditions for both groups.

130

131 **Filming of the hens**

132 For two days prior the experiments, hens were familiarized with the observers who remained
133 seated on the ground, and with the camcorders and tripods used later. During this time,
134 observers maintained a calm presence in the flocks and fed hens with mealworms. Hens were
135 confident with the observers during the experiment; they came into contact spontaneously
136 during the whole duration of the study.

137 Each hen was filmed with two camcorders with 4K quality (Sony FDR-AX53; automatic white
138 balance function activated) while conducting several routine behaviours and during two
139 behavioural tests. During daily routines, observers focused on filming four predefined
140 positively valenced behaviours and one negatively valenced: Resting (lying with eyes opened
141 or closed and sometimes pecking the ground), Feeding (eating from the feed trough or grass),
142 Dustbathing (hens squatting in dusty areas of the ground, doing vertical wing shaking,
143 scratching, bill raking, head rubbing, side lying and side rubbing; preliminary phase of pecking
144 and scratching was excluded), Preening (feathers manipulation with the beak, excluding
145 sequences following a dustbathe), and Alert (immobile posture with raised neck following a
146 sudden event). At least twenty minutes of film (distributed along the observational period) was
147 collected for each routine behaviour and hen. With the exception of Alert, we have excluded all
148 cases where interactions with conspecifics were observed. The two behavioural tests were
149 performed to enrich the situations studied. Capture test was negatively valenced and Reward
150 test positively valenced. During the Capture test, each hen was captured as calmly as possible
151 by the same observer. It was the first time they were captured by the observer. The hen was
152 then carried to a specific location of the enclosure to be filmed. They were held in the hands of
153 the observer approximatively 1 meter above the ground for 1 minute (wings were maintained
154 against the hen's body to prevent movements). Each of the right and left profiles of the hen's
155 head was filmed for 30 seconds. During Reward test, hens were filmed eating a highly appealing
156 food, i.e. mealworm. They were individually tested inside their usual enclosure in an arena

157 delimited by wire-mesh (P-hens: l = 89 cm, w = 89 cm, h = 56 cm; M-hens: 118 cm x 59 cm x
158 58 cm) covered with cardboard (h = 33 cm) to avoid visual contact with conspecifics. A
159 transparent glass dish ($\varnothing = 7$ cm, h = 4 cm) containing about 30 mealworms covered with litter
160 was placed inside the arena. All hens had free access to the arena from approximately 36 hours
161 before being tested. They had also been previously familiarized to eat mealworms from the dish
162 inside the arena. On the day of the test, hens spontaneously entered the arena, which was
163 immediately closed. Two observers each filmed the head of the hen for 150 seconds.

164 Each group of hens (M-hens and P-hens) was filmed by two observers over a four-week period.
165 Films were performed between 10:00 and 18:00 to avoid sunrise and sunset (at this season the
166 sun is high in the sky; the sun rises at 6:00-6:40 and sets at 21:25-22:00, zenith at 14:00). The
167 first two weeks focused on filming routine behaviours. The behavioural tests were conducted
168 during the third week to obtain hens highly familiarized with the observers. They were repeated
169 twice to be sure to obtain sufficient data (images with complete head profile): the same day
170 (morning and afternoon) for Capture tests, in the morning of two different days for Rewarding
171 tests. Capture tests were performed first. The fourth week was used to complete films focused
172 on routine behaviour difficult to obtain (mainly feeding and dustbathing sequences). Hen
173 identification was based on physical characteristics (colour, comb shape and size...), but also
174 on coloured rings put on one leg (before the experiment) in case of the M-hens.

175 The behaviours and tests selected for this study allowed us to observe a wide range of emotional
176 situations. Alert is a response to a perceived danger (e.g. predator such as Common buzzard),
177 and capture and manual restraint by human is a frightening event [23] (Jones 1996). Both
178 situations generate affective states associated with fear in domestic fowl. Dustbathing and
179 consumption of mealworms (Reward test) have rewarding effects. Both are highly motivated
180 behaviours extensively studied (and used as rewarding stimulus in case of mealworms) in
181 domestic fowl, looking at behaviour but also neurobiological substrates. Domestic fowl work

182 for access to mealworms or to dusty substrate to perform dustbathing, and show positive
183 anticipation behaviours [28-30]. Resting, feeding and preening are behaviours that contribute
184 to the maintenance of the health and for preening also the appropriate structure of the feathers
185 (e.g. for insulation). They are performed in situations of absence of threat, i.e. calm situations,
186 and are often considered to be associated with positive affective states (e.g. [24,31]). Preening
187 is performed when hens are in a state of low arousal and relaxation (e.g. [25,32]). Resting is
188 closely related to preening and other maintenance behaviours, likely to use time optimally when
189 there is a low risk of danger [33]. Food consumption has hedonic value [34].

190

191 **Image extraction, selection and analysis**

192 From each film, images were automatically extracted every two seconds using the “burst
193 capture” function of the free software GOM Player. We then manually selected those images
194 containing a profile of a hen with all the unfeathered areas of the face visible: appendices (comb,
195 wattles) and denuded skin of the face (cheeks, ear lobes) (Fig 1a). Only images with uniform
196 light and without direct sun were kept. Then, we selected at random thirty images for each hen
197 and situation using a python script that avoided, as far as possible, to select images from a same
198 film. This method allows maximizing the number of sequences sampled. Images came, as far
199 as possible, from different days and behavioural sequences. We multiplied the sampling to
200 minimise any bias that might have occurred if only a few images per situation and per hen had
201 been used. It was difficult to calibrate the lighting conditions during filming. Domestic hens are
202 fast-moving animals with rapid head movements, so it is not possible to place a colour standard
203 close to the head inside the frames. In addition, moving around the animals trying to place
204 colour standard charts would have been disturbing for the hens. For some behaviours and hens
205 the number of useable images was less than 30 (S1 Table).

206

207 **Fig 1. Profiles of a hen showing different feather positions and skin redness, and the four**
208 **regions of interest where redness was sampled.**

209 **(a) Illustration of the four region of interest (arrows). (b) Locations where skin redness**
210 **was sampled (black squares, 10 x 10 pixels squares). (b,c) Location where feathers'**
211 **position was observed (blue rectangle). Figures illustrate Eden (Meusienne hen) with (a,**
212 **b) feathers labelled as sleeked or (c) fluffed and with (a) low or (b, c) high skin redness.**
213 **Pictures are extracted from (a) Resting, (b) Capture, and (c) Dustbathing situations.**

214

215 All images were then analysed by the same experimenter using ImageJ software [35]. Feathers
216 on the top of the head (i.e. crown feathers as defined by Kaplan [36]) were labelled as: fluffed
217 (tip of the feathers visible), sleeked (tip of the feathers not visible) or impossible to decide (Fig
218 1 b,c). In addition, as previously performed on blue- and-yellow macaws (*Ara ararauna*; see
219 [20] for more details), we collected the mean value of red (R), green(G) and blue (B) on squares
220 of 10 x 10 pixels located on each region of interest (ROI) and calculated the redness of the skin
221 for each, as $R/(R+G+B)$. This method is used to normalise luminance. The number of squares
222 per ROI varied depending on to the surface visible on the profile analysed. We tried to obtain
223 three squares of 100 pixels each for comb, wattles, cheeks and two squares for ear lobes (area
224 of smaller size; Fig 1b). In order to control for the white balance, we added a square of the same
225 size (100 pixels) on the white feathers in each image (Fig 1b). The median redness values
226 obtained for the white feathers were 0.328 [0.315-0.333] and 0.329 [0.322-0.332] for M-hens
227 and P-hens respectively, quite similar to the 0.333 the value for the pure white standard
228 ($R=G=B$; S2 Fig.).

229

230

231 **Statistical analysis**

232 All data analyses were conducted in R 4.2.2 [37] (R Core Team, 2019).

233 **Variation of feather position and skin redness of the face depending on the** 234 **situation.**

235 Feather position. To determine if head feather position varied depending on the situation, we
236 used a binomial Generalized Linear Mixed Model (GLMM) (lme4 package [38]), with Situation
237 as fixed factor and Hen as random factor, followed by post-hoc comparisons with p-value
238 adjusted by Tukey (emmeans package [39]). Images with posturing observations labelled
239 “impossible to decide” and two P-hens with curly plumage were removed from the analysis. As
240 feathers were never fluffed during Reward situation in M-hens, one sleeked and one fluffed
241 value were added to each hen for each situation to avoid convergence problem of the model.

242 Skin redness. To describe skin redness variations depending on the situation, two analyses were
243 performed. First, we performed a hierarchical cluster analysis (mixOmics package [40]) based
244 on the median redness the four ROIs. Hen effect was included as random factor. This
245 exploratory analysis was used to identify if some situations were characterized by similar skin
246 redness of the face (situations in a same cluster) and others can be dissociated on this basis, i.e.
247 skin redness of the face (situations located in different clusters). Second, we compared skin
248 redness between situations for each of the four ROIs. Redness values were log2 transformed to
249 obtain normality of the residuals and homogeneity of the variance assumptions required for the
250 analyses. The validity of these assumptions was verified using the DHARMA package [41]. We
251 used a Generalized Linear Mixed Model (GLMM) with Situation, ROI and their interaction as
252 fixed-factors and hen as random factor (lme4 package). We then compared situations using

253 emmeans package (p-values adjusted by Tukey) when the factor was significant according to
254 the ANOVA.

255 **Variation of skin redness of the face depending on arousal and emotional** 256 **valence of the situation**

257 To go further in our analysis on skin redness, we grouped situations with similar arousal or
258 valence based on theoretical frameworks on affective states [27,31,42] and literature on poultry
259 behaviour (see above, section 2.2). According to these authors and others, situations that induce
260 fear-related behaviours, have rewarding effect, or calm states are thought to be associated to
261 different affective states characterised by negative valence with high arousal, positive valence
262 with high arousal, and positive valence with low arousal respectively.

263 Arousal. We compared situations with high versus low arousal. High arousal included Capture,
264 Alert (fear-related behaviours), Dustbathing and Reward (behaviours with appetitive
265 motivational states, i. e. with rewarding effects), whereas Low arousal included Feeding,
266 Resting and Preening (maintenance behaviour, calm states). Even if feeding is considered as
267 rewarding in the literature and as such inducing an emotion with high arousal, we observed very
268 different levels of excitation depending on whether birds were consuming usual non-restricted
269 food or grasses, or highly appetitive food such as insects, mealworms, etc. Furthermore, if both
270 have positive hedonic values, novelty, attention or anticipation are goal-oriented behaviour
271 likely not required in case of ad libitum food according to Saper et al [34]. Therefore, we
272 considered that during Feeding arousal level was low compared to Reward, in which
273 mealworms were given.

274 Valence. We compared situations with 1. negative valence /high arousal (V-/A+; Capture,
275 Alert), 2. positive valence /high arousal (V+/A+; Dustbathing, Reward), and 3. positive valence
276 /low arousal (V+/A-; Feeding, Resting, Preening). Arousal level was considered in association

277 with valence as we observed an effect of arousal level on skin redness. This allowed comparison
278 between situations with similar valence but different arousal levels and allowed access to three
279 affective states: fear-related, with rewarding effect and calm states. For both Arousal and
280 Valence, we used the same model and log2 transformation as previously with Arousal or
281 Valence, ROI and their interaction as fixed factors and hen as random factor.

282 All data are presented as medians with interquartile ranges. Test significance was considered at
283 $p \leq 0.05$

284

285

286 **Results**

287

288 **Feather position and skin redness of the face varied with the** 289 **situations**

290 **Feather position**

291 In M-hens and P-hens, the percentage of profiles where head feathers were fluffed varied across
292 situation (M-hens: $\text{Chi}^2 = 202.0$, P-hens: $\text{Chi}^2 = 178.9$; d.f. =6 and $p < 0.001$ in both cases). In
293 M-hens the percentage of images with feather fluffed was significantly different for
294 Dustbathing, Preening and Resting situations (median ≥ 40 % in all three cases) compared to
295 Capture, Alert, Feeding and Reward (0 % in all four cases) situations ($p < 0.001$ in all cases;
296 Table 1). In P-hens results were similar except for Alert. The percentage of images with feather
297 fluffed was significantly different for Alert, Dustbathing, Preening and Resting situations

298 (median ≥ 56 % in all four cases) compared to Capture (9 %), Feeding and Reward (0 % in both
 299 cases) situations ($p < 0.001$ in all cases).

300

301 **Table 1. Percentage of images where feathers were fluffed depending on the situation. (a)**
 302 **M-hens. (b) P-hens. A value of 0 means that feathers were sleeked on all the images.**
 303 **Percentages with different letters in a row are significantly different.**

Group	Alert	Capture	Reward	Feeding	Dustbathing	Preening	Resting
M-hens (%)	0 [0-6] a	0 [0-59] a	0 [0-0] a	0 [0-0] a	40 [37-66] b	52 [46-64] b	44 [33-65] b
P-hens (%)	100 [52-100] b	9 [0-88] a	0 [0-2] a	0 [0-2] a	56 [21-82] b	82 [50-100] b	68 [28-90] b

304

305 **Skin redness**

306 Hierarchical cluster analysis that took into account the redness of the skin of the comb, wattles,
 307 ear lobes and cheeks revealed two clusters in both groups (Fig 2a,b). Cluster 1 was comprised
 308 of situations where hens displayed high redness levels of the ROIs, whereas cluster 2 was
 309 comprised of situations where hens displayed low redness levels. Overall, the cluster analyses
 310 for M- and P-hens were similar. All M-hens and P-hens in the Capture situation and all M-hens
 311 and most of P-hens in the Alert situation were in cluster 1. In contrast, M- and P-hens in the
 312 Feeding, Resting and Preening situations were in cluster 2. Hens in the Dustbathing situation
 313 were split across clusters 1 and 2. The main difference between groups concerned the Reward
 314 situation for which M-hens were in Cluster 1 while P-hens were in Cluster 2.

315

316 **Fig 2. Dendrogram (left hand side of the figures) and table from hierarchical cluster**
 317 **analyses of the redness of the skin for the four ROIs.**

318 **(a) M-hens. (b) P-hens. The heatmap contains the tested situations (Alert, Capture,**
319 **Reward... in red, blue, green...) in rows and ROI (wattles, comb, cheeks, ear lobes) in**
320 **columns with red colour indicating high-level of redness, blue colour low-level, and yellow**
321 **colour being between the two. Tables indicate for each situation the number of hens in**
322 **each cluster (M-hens, n = 7, P-hens, n = 10).**

323

324 The ANOVA between full and reduced models revealed significant effects of the two main
325 factors (Situation and ROI) and an interaction effect between the two in both groups (M-hens
326 Situation: $F(6, 162) = 138.73$, ROI: $F(3, 162) = 137.41$, $p < 0.001$ in both cases, Interaction:
327 $F(3, 162) = 2.45$, $p = 0.002$ - P-hens Situation: $F(6, 243) = 138.73$, ROI: $F(3, 243) = 122.46$,
328 Interaction: $F(18, 243) = 2.72$, $p < 0.001$ in all three cases). In M-hens (Fig 3a) the redness of
329 the four ROIs (comb, wattles, ear lobes, cheeks) was significantly higher in Alert, Capture and
330 Reward situations than in Feeding, Preening and Resting situations ($p < 0.001$ in all cases).
331 Dustbathing situation had an intermediate position with slight variations according to the ROI.
332 For ear lobes and cheeks, redness in this situation were significantly lower than in Alert,
333 Capture and Reward situations and higher than in Feeding, Preening and Resting situations (p
334 < 0.03 in all cases). In P-hens (Fig 3b) cheeks was the ROI that best discriminates the situation
335 and results were quite similar to those observed in M-hens: the redness was significantly higher
336 in Alert, Capture, Reward and Dustbathing situations than in Feeding, Preening and Resting
337 situations ($p < 0.016$).

338

339 **Fig 3. Median and interquartile range of the redness of the skin for wattles, comb, cheeks**
340 **and ear lobes depending on the situation.**

341 **(a) M-hens. (b) P-hens. Situations with different subscripts differed significantly (GLMM**
342 **on log₂ transformed data with Tukey adjustment for two-by-two comparisons).**

343

344 **Skin redness varied depending on the arousal and emotional**
345 **valence of the situation**

346 **Arousal**

347 The ANOVA between full and reduced models revealed in both groups significant effects of
348 the two main factors (Arousal and ROI) and an interaction effect between the two (M-hens:
349 Arousal $F(1, 182) = 470.56$, ROI $F(3, 182) = 85.07$, $p < 0.001$ in both cases, Interaction $F(3,$
350 $182) = 3.93$, $p = 0.010$ – P-hens: Arousal $F(1, 223) = 149.30$, ROI $F(3, 223) = 60.26$, Interaction
351 $F(3, 223) = 6.11$, $p < 0.001$ in the three cases; Fig 4a,b). Hens displayed a higher level of redness
352 during the high- compared to the low-arousal situations in all ROIs ($p < 0.001$ in all cases).

353

354 **Fig 4. Redness (median and interquartile range) of the skin for wattles, comb, cheeks and**
355 **ear lobes depending on the arousal of the situation.**

356 **(a) M-hens. (b) P-hens. Low arousal includes Feeding, Resting and Preening; High arousal**
357 **includes Capture, Alert, Dustbathing and Reward. *****: $p < 0.001$ (GLMM on log₂**
358 **transformed data with Tukey adjustment for two-by-two comparisons).**

359

360 **Valence**

361 In both groups, significant effects of the two main factors (Valence and ROI) and an interaction
362 effect between the two were revealed by the ANOVA (M-hens: Valence $F(2, 178) = 293.77$,
363 ROI $F(3, 178) = 102.53$, $p < 0.001$ in both cases, Interaction $F(6, 178) = 3.83$, $p = 0.001$ – P-
364 hens: Valence $F(2, 259) = 133.43$, ROI $F(3, 259) = 81.53$, $p < 0.001$ in both cases, Interaction
365 $F(6, 259) = 3.83$, $p = 0.001$; Fig 5a,b). Cheek and ear lobe redness in both groups, and also
366 wattles redness in P-hens, were significantly higher in emotional situations with negative
367 valence (V-/A+) than in emotional situations with positive valence (whether arousal is positive
368 or negative: V+/A+ and V+/A-). Skin redness significantly decreases from V-/A+ to V+/A+ (p
369 ≤ 0.004) and from V+/A+ to V+/A- ($p < 0.006$ in all cases). For the skin of the comb and wattles
370 in M-hens, no significant difference was observed between negative and positive valence when
371 arousal was high (V-/A+ vs V+/A+; $p = 0.148$ and $p = 0.683$ respectively).

372

373 **Fig 5. Redness (median and interquartile range) of the skin for wattles, comb, cheek and**
374 **ear lobes depending on the valence and arousal of the situation. (a) M-hens. (b) P-hens.**
375 **Negative valence / high arousal (V-/A+) includes Capture and Alert, positive valence / high**
376 **arousal (V+/A+) includes Dustbathing and Reward, positive valence / low arousal (V+/A)**
377 **include Feeding, Resting and Preening). Situations with different subscripts differed**
378 **significantly (GLMM on log2 transformed data with Tukey adjustment for two-by-two**
379 **comparisons).**

380

381

382 **Discussion**

383 Our results show clearly that hens express facial expressions by means of subtle transitory
384 changes in feather position and in the level of skin redness of the denuded areas of their head.
385 Feather position and face redness vary depending on the situation experienced and thus provide
386 useful information on the emotional state being experienced. Specifically, we provide evidence
387 for the first time that domestic hens blush in situations of high arousal (negatively valenced, but
388 also positively valenced). Similarity was observed in the facial expression of the two strains
389 studied, which underlines the robustness of our observations and suggest a functional role of
390 these facial displays.

391 Crown feather position changed depending on the situation experienced. In situations where
392 hens were eating (Feeding, Reward) feathers were sleeked for almost all profiles as observed
393 in blue-and-yellow macaws and sulphur-crested cockatoos (*Cacatua galerita*; [43,44]). Across
394 the negatively valenced situations, we found varied feather positions. Feathers were observed
395 mainly sleeked during Capture. Interestingly, the only difference in regards to feather position
396 between the groups was observed for the Alert situation in which P-hens displayed a high
397 proportion of profiles with fluffed feathers while M-hens displayed a very low proportion. A
398 difference in the emotional experience between strains cannot be excluded, but it is more likely
399 that these contrasted facial displays are linked to the biological significance of the situations
400 encountered. The causes of the spontaneous alert behaviour were unpredictable and differed
401 between the two groups. For P-hens alert behaviour was mainly caused by the vocalisations of
402 raptors (also by dog barking or plane noise passing by at low altitude), whereas for M-hens it
403 was initiated by alert vocalizations from conspecifics living in proximity. Several Galliformes
404 species including domestic fowl use different alarm calls in presence of terrestrial or aerial
405 predators [45]. Roosters also modulate alarm call duration as a function of their vulnerability
406 (close to a refuge *versus* out in the open) or of the proximity of conspecifics [46]. As these
407 studies indicate that domestic fowl show variation in perceived risks, here hens might have

408 expressed different facial displays depending on the type of alarming situation. P-hen fluffed
409 position of the feathers might have a camouflage function. When they were in an open area they
410 ran under a tree and looked at the sky, which strengthens this interpretation. If fluffed feathers
411 had a camouflage function, this facial display might be biologically irrelevant in the case of M-
412 hens. These hens were in close vicinity of the vocalizing conspecifics which had caused their
413 alert behaviour. Furthermore, some of them also emitted vocalisations (which was not observed
414 with P-hens). In positively valenced situations such as Resting, Preening and Dustbathing,
415 feathers were fluffed in a high proportion of the profiles. This percentage likely reflects the
416 succession of different phases (including sometimes pauses of a few seconds) during preening
417 and dustbathing behaviour (e.g. [32,47]). But also in resting behaviour, since different levels of
418 vigilance occurs (from sparsely pecking on the ground to sleeping with closed eyes). Fluffing
419 of head feathers appears to be a relevant indicator of positive emotional states, that can be
420 observed in different situations and species. Indeed, this facial display has been observed during
421 maintenance behaviour, resting and positive social interactions in Psittacidae (macaws and
422 cockatoo) as well as with macaws in presence of their caretaker, or with Japanese quail during
423 dustbathing behaviour [20,43,44, 48]. In resting birds this facial display seems to be highly
424 conserved between bird species. Beyond our observation on domestic hens, a species highly
425 selected by humans, and Psittacidae, it has been reported in crows (*Corvus frugilegus*;
426 V. Dufour, personal communication), finches, doves and pigeons [49] (Morris 1956). Beyond
427 the temperature function, fluffing of body feathers at rest gives a rounded appearance that
428 stimulates clumping in finches and concentrates mutual preening on the head when only head
429 and neck plumage are ruffled [49]. These behaviours (clumping and mutual preening) facilitate
430 affiliation and group cohesion. Similar social function of feather fluffing probably exists in
431 domestic hens. All these analogies (similarities in response to similar selection pressure, as

432 defined by Waller and Micheletta [2] are in favour of an evolutionary continuity between bird
433 species and, as such, could help to elucidate their communicative function.

434 Our most exciting and informative result concerns blushing and its relation with emotions. The
435 skin redness of the face was lower in situations with positive valence and low arousal where
436 birds are calm and contented (Resting, Preening and Feeding), than in situations with negative
437 valence and high arousal associated to fear-related behaviour (Alert and Capture). Skin redness
438 during situations with positive valence and high arousal that have rewarding effects
439 (Dustbathing and Reward) was intermediate. This suggests a continuum of skin redness
440 providing subtle information about emotional affects rather than the simpler positive/negative
441 valence dichotomy. That said, it is also possible that these intermediate redness values are the
442 result of the dynamics of arousal level during these situations, especially in the case of
443 dustbathing. Birds are highly motivated to dustbathe and dustbathing behaviour probably elicits
444 a feeling of pleasure [50]. This behaviour can last more than twenty minutes if birds are
445 undisturbed [51] and has a complex structure, as mentioned above. We observed alternation of
446 phases of high and low redness (as well different level of feather erection), likely due to an
447 alternation of high and low arousal. So far, the mechanism regulating facial blushing in birds is
448 unknown. Anyway, it is unlikely that the higher redness observed in the fear-related behaviours
449 resulted from differences in physical exertion compared to rewarding situations. Indeed, the
450 hens were more active during the dustbathes or reward tests than during the capture or alert
451 situations where they were motionless. Furthermore, redness was low during preening and
452 eating, where hens were physically active, in the same way as during resting.

453 Cheeks and ear lobes appear more relevant to reveal emotions in domestic hens than comb or
454 wattles. These denuded regions, provide the clearest information for distinguishing between
455 valence and arousal levels in both strains. While the redness of all the ROIs changed with the
456 arousal level (high arousal being associated to higher redness), only the redness of cheeks and

457 ear lobes varied depending on the valence of the situation. In situations with high arousal,
458 redness was highest in situations with negative valence than in positive ones. The different
459 regions of the face might have different communicative functions for the hens. Comb and
460 wattles increase with sexual maturation both in male and in female domestic hens. Comb and
461 ornament size and colour communicate information on, or are associated with mating success,
462 dominance, sperm quality or health status in several avian species (e.g. [22,52-56]). The
463 physiological characteristics of these denuded skin areas might be different from that of cheeks
464 and ear lobes. Comb and wattles might be less appropriate than cheeks and ear lobes to
465 communicate emotional states to conspecifics, even in juvenile hens for which comb and
466 wattles are not fully developed and coloured. This hypothesis requires further evidence from
467 adult hens. Our results should be considered as a first step because they were obtained on two
468 groups of relatively small size. However, we have replicated the data on the two strains studied
469 (Pekin, Meusienne), which reinforce the possibility generalising our results.

470 Some limitations about our results on blushing can be raised due to our methodological
471 approach. The naturalistic approach we used makes the precise calibration of light conditions
472 during filming difficult. At this date we did not find good solution to insert standard charts
473 inside film without interfering with bird behaviour. Indeed, our method is based on studying
474 free living birds and our objective was to restrict as far as we can the perturbation induce by
475 filming. It is why we choose to measure redness on the white head feathers on each image to
476 validate our method. Variations observed on white feathers showed that colours on images were
477 quite well balanced since we find a redness of 0.33 (which indicate that R, G, and B values for
478 white feathers were similar). Furthermore, the variability observed for white feather redness
479 was far below the variations observed between the situations tested when significant differences
480 were obtained. The naturalistic approach also makes difficult to control with precision for
481 temperature or wind. However, temperature did not vary very much during our study and our

482 results cannot be explained by thermoregulation variations. Indeed, the blushing measured in
483 our study appear in few seconds and is transitory (a video can be seen on S3 Video). Neither
484 can blushing be explained by variations of body temperature associated with activity, as
485 mentioned above. Whatever these limitations, this study brings new knowledges to the
486 understanding of expression of emotion in free living hens. It is the first to assess blushing in
487 birds in such a variety of affective states. The significance of this blushing to regulate
488 interactions between hen rest to be investigated.

489 Some potential sources of uncertainty exist in the interpretation of our results. First, the two-
490 dimensional model used in the present study that classified emotions depending on valence and
491 arousal is useful to decode emotions, but like every model it has some limitations. Emotions
492 are not fixed, they are part of a dynamic process. For example, motivation to obtain a reward
493 can be followed by the satisfaction of having obtained it. Then, if the emotion is pleasant in
494 both cases the arousal level evolved from high during pursuing and achieving the reward to low
495 when the reward has been obtained. When the goal has been achieved, a phase of contentment
496 appears. Such a dynamic seems to exist during dustbathing for example. Arousal level might
497 vary during this long-lasting behaviour constituted of different phases. The ability to analyze a
498 high number of images on the sequences filmed would help to capture with more precision the
499 dynamics of the emotion experienced, but adequate methods are currently lacking. Second, the
500 combination of feather position and skin redness of the face likely help to interpret expressions,
501 as the colour of the human face when added to facial-muscular features. Indeed, the colour of
502 the human face facilitates the disambiguation of emotion in the case of confusing facial-
503 muscular expression, such as in early dynamic sequence of anger or disgust [13]. Due to the
504 impossibility to measure feather erection with a nominal scale on the images obtained in the
505 present study, it was impossible to combine these data with the skin redness of the face in a
506 statistical model. However, Benitez-Quiroz et al [12] showed that human emotions can be

507 decoded using facial colour alone, without the involvement of facial musculature. Third,
508 communication is multi-modal [57]. The posture or vocalizations emitted probably facilitate
509 the interpretation of the facial expressions by conspecifics. As the birds observed lived in a
510 group and in a very rich auditory environment, we were unable to discriminate properly the
511 vocal signals emitted simultaneously with facial expressions. Identifying with certainty the
512 vocalizing individuals was not possible.

513 The characterisation of facial expression during activities associated to low arousal positive
514 state of contentment (low redness and crown feather fluffed) is of great interest for studies on
515 bird welfare. This facial display indicates that birds are calm and secure. A state that enables
516 affiliation and attachment, but also well-being in humans [42]. Decoding this type of emotion
517 is of particular interest in domestic fowl, a species which lives in close contact with humans,
518 and more broadly for all bird species interacting with humans. Descovich et al [7] claims that
519 facial expression measurement could be very useful to assess welfare in mammals. Our results
520 show that birds, and particularly domestic ones, should clearly not be excluded from research
521 on facial expression of emotions, especially by researchers working on bird welfare and
522 searching for indicators of positive emotions. Indeed, such indicators are currently sorely
523 lacking. These commercially important species are in dire need of a better understanding of
524 how they experience and express both positive and negative emotions. This study constitutes a
525 first step in the development of a methodology that could be used in the future to obtain reliable
526 indicators of emotions.

527

528

529 **Conclusions**

530 We describe for the first-time facial expression in domestic fowl by means of variation in crown
531 feather fluffing and skin redness. Domestic fowl showed fluffing, blushing or both in specific
532 emotional contexts varying in both valence and arousal levels. We show that blushing of the
533 face is observed in a domestic avian species, which emotional and cognitive capacities are likely
534 underestimated. The ability to use facial skin redness to infer the emotional state opens a wide
535 window to being able to better understand the emotional experiences of birds. Furthermore, the
536 evidence of blushing in birds experiencing positive and negative emotions, as it is observed in
537 humans, is in favour of an evolutionary continuity in this expressive system between species
538 with sophisticated social interactions. The assumption of Darwin that blushing is “the most
539 human of all expressions” (1872) still highlighted nowadays (e.g. [58]) is seriously weakened
540 by our results, which question the phylogenetic origin of emotional facial blushing in the animal
541 kingdom.

542

543 **Data accessibility.** The data and code supporting the findings in this paper are available in an
544 open access repository [59].

545

546

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550

551

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719

720

721 **Supporting information**

722

723 S1 Table. Number of images per situation and hen for M-hens and P-hens.

724 S2 Fig. Redness of white feathers per situation.

725 S3 Video. Illustration of a rapid blushing following a sudden noise in a Pékin hen

726

a M-hens

Alert Capture Reward Dustbathing Feeding Resting Preening

a

M-hens

b

P-hens

High Low

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Supporting Information
S3_Video.mp4

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